

Supplementary Information

Harnessing $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{-WS}_2$ Nanostructures as Efficient Energy Scaffoldings for Photocatalytic Hydrogen Generation

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Fig. S1 Optimised monolayer structure of a. WS₂ b. Ti₃C₂ and c. heterostructure of WS₂/Ti₃C₂.

Fig. S2 Phonon dispersion of WS₂/Ti₃C₂ heterostructure.

Fig. S3 Raman spectra of Ti₃C₂, WS₂ and WS₂/Ti₃C₂ nanostructures.

Fig. S4 XPS Spectra of Ti₃C₂, WS₂ and WS₂/Ti₃C₂ nanostructures.

Fig. S5 Energy Dispersive X-ray (EDS) spectra of Ti_3C_2 with elemental composition and the respective elemental mapping.

Fig. S6 EDS spectra of WS₂ with elemental contents and the corresponding elemental mapping.

Fig. S7 EDS spectra of $\text{WS}_2/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ composite, relative composition of constituent elements and elemental mapping.

Fig. S8 (a) STEM image, (b) AFM image and (c) height profile of WS₂ nanoflakes.

Fig. S9 EIS spectra of WS₂/Ti₃C₂ nanostructures before and after stability test.